

TIME-DEPENDENT FAILURE OF POLYMERIC COMPOSITES
WITH DELAMINATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the creep response and failure of graphite/epoxy composites containing delaminations. Creep tests were performed on double cantilever beam specimens with (0) and (90) laminates at elevated temperature. The crack opening displacement and deformation field near the tip of a delamination are measured as a function of time using both the COD gage and the moire interferometry. The measured displacements are compared with predictions from viscoelastic finite element analyses and good agreement between the two results is observed.

KEY WORDS: Composites; Delamination; Creep; Failure; Finite Element Analysis; Moire Interferometry.

1. INTRODUCTION

Delamination has been found to be one of the most critical type of defects in polymeric composites, as it can significantly reduce the compressive load carrying capability of a structure. Past studies on delamination fracture in composites have been limited to the case of quasi-static loading. Since mechanical properties of a polymeric material exhibit strong time-dependent effects, a matrix dominated failure mode such as delamination is expected to be dependent upon time and temperature as well [1-4]. Thus, it is important to understand the response of a delamination to thermal environment over a long term period in order to design a durable composite structure.

The present study investigates the time-dependent failure of a delamination at elevated temperature. The deformation fields near the tip of a delamination in graphite/epoxy composites are determined as a function of time using a moiré interferometry technique. The time-varying crack opening displacements away from the delamination tip are measured by a COD gauge. The experimental data are compared with results obtained from a special finite element method developed for viscoelastic composites. In addition, the effect of layup orientation on delamination growth characteristics is also studied.

2. VISCOELASTIC ANALYSIS

Analysis of viscoelastic behavior in composites is complicated by the history dependent nature of the problem. The numerical solution for complex geometry generally requires enormous computing time and storage. To overcome such difficulties, a special numerical algorithm has been developed recently by Lin and Hwang [3] and Lin and Yi [4] for the efficient and accurate solution of viscoelastic boundary value problems. The method uses the integral form of viscoelastic constitutive relation [5] with the relaxation modulus represented by an exponential series. The finite element method is employed for spatial discretization of the domain which yields a system of integral equations. A recursive formula has been derived for the numerical integration of the resulting equilibrium equations, after which the internal stresses and strain histories can be determined. This analysis method is adopted in the present study to calculate the time-varying crack opening displacement in a double cantilever beam specimen. Details of the numerical analysis procedure can be found in [3,4] and will not be repeated here.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The IM7/8551-7 graphite/epoxy composite was used in this study. This material was chosen due to its relatively high sensitivity to time-dependent effects. The test specimen configuration is a 11.43 cm (4.5 in.) long by 2.54 cm (1 in.) wide double cantilever beam (DCB) with 50 plies of (0) or (90) laminates (approximately 0.673 cm or 0.265 in. thick). The (0) specimen has fiber orientation parallel to the initial delamination and is referred as "parallel" specimen while the 90 specimen is denoted as "normal" specimen. Each test sample contains a teflon strip of 3.175 cm (1.25 in.) long on the midplane of the laminate to simulate an initial delamination.

Quasi-static tests were first conducted to obtain the basic load-crack opening displacement (COD) curve so that the load level for the subsequent creep test could be appropriately chosen. Creep tests were then performed on a custom made apparatus under a constant gravity weight. Loads were applied to the specimen through a bonded aluminum hinge which would allow for a free rotation. The crack opening

gage was used to measure the displacement at a distance from the crack tip. In addition, a moire interferometry setup was used to measure the entire deformation field in the DCB specimen as a function of time at a given temperature. The complete experimental setup consists of a creep load frame, a 35 mW He-Ne laser and various optical components mounted on a holographic platform (see Figure 1) [6,7]. The diffraction grating on the DCB specimen has 600 lines/mm which yields a resolution of 1/1200 mm per fringe for the u and v displacements. Details of the experimental procedure can be found in [8].

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 (0) Specimens Results of static tests for parallel specimens tested at room temperature and 121°C (250°F) are shown in Figure 2. The slope of the curve for SP-2 specimen at 121°C is approximately 95% of SP-1 specimen tested at room temperature. After a maximum load is reached crack propagation occurs, and the COD of SP-2 is much larger than that of SP-1 due to the degradation of material properties at elevated temperature. Figure 3 shows the crack mouth opening displacements for parallel specimens subjected to initial loads prior to creep tests. The load levels applied were : 311.4 N (70 lbs) for CP1, 333.6 N (75 lbs) for CP2, and 378.1 N (85 lbs) for CP-3. Note that the relationship between the applied load and crack mouth opening displacement is linear for all three specimens. These data compare well with the results obtained from the finite element analysis.

The time-dependent response of CP-1, CP-2, and CP-3 specimens at 121°C over a short time period is shown in Figure 4. The loads in Figure 4 have been normalized with respect to the applied load which is different for each specimen. Specimens CP-1 and CP-2 did not fail but specimen CP-3 failed via unstable crack propagation at 378.1 N after 6.5 hours. The response of CP-2 specimen to 333.6 N load over a period of 330 hours is shown in Figure 5. The analytical results based on a finite element algorithm in [4] are also shown in Figures 4 and 5 for comparison. As can be seen, the predictions agree well with experimental data up to the time when delamination propagates. Since the finite element results are obtained from a stationary delamination, they are not suitable for comparison once the delamination advances.

The deformations in the crack tip region were measured by the moire interferometry. Typical v (opening) displacement fields from CP-2 specimen are shown in Figure 6(a) and 6(b) for a time period of 60 hours and 170 hours, respectively. Note that Figure 6(b) has much denser fringes and thus larger strain values than Figure 6(a).

Static and creep tests were also conducted for one parallel specimen at 149°C (300°F). At this temperature, the static COD vs. load curve becomes highly nonlinear. The specimen failed after 4.5 hours under 244.8 N. The rupture time is extremely short

compared to other samples tested at 121°C. This is due to the fact that the matrix property degrades drastically at a temperature close to its glass transition temperature. More test data are needed in this temperature range in order to draw a meaningful conclusion.

4.2 (90) Specimens The load vs. COD curves for normal specimens at room temperature and 121°C are shown in Figure 7. Since normal specimens are matrix dominated, the maximum loads in these samples are much smaller than those of parallel specimens. Figure 8 depicts the static load-displacement relation for three normal specimens before creep testing. The load levels were: 71.2 N (16 lbs) for CN-1 and CN-3, and 84.5 N (19 lbs) for CN-2. There are some differences between the test data and the finite element results. The discrepancy is believed to be caused by a simplified point load boundary condition used in the analysis. The actual load distribution in a DCB specimen is much more complex than a point load, especially for a short delamination.

The time-dependent response of normal specimens at 121°C are shown in Figure 9 as a function of time. The CN-1 specimen was loaded up to 71.2 N and failed after 12.5 hours while specimen CN-2 failed after 1 hour and 45 minutes under 84.5 N. CN-3 was loaded to 16 lbs for 4.5 hours, then unloaded for residual strength testing. In these specimens, little delamination growth was observed prior to final failure. Failure occurred as a result of the transverse subcracks formed around graphite fibers near the delamination tip. Results from the viscoelastic finite element analysis are also shown in Figure 9 for comparison. The analysis compares well with experiment within a short time period. However, as time increases, the discrepancy between these two results becomes larger. This can be attributed to the inaccurate material properties used in the analysis.

5. CONCLUSION

The time-dependent fracture of graphite/epoxy composites with delaminations has been studied both experimentally and analytically. It was found that stable delamination growth prevails in (0) laminates at 121°C prior to final specimen failure. The (90) sample develops transverse subcracks and fails without significant growth. The crack-mouth opening displacements in both (0) and (90) laminates increase with time and can be predicted by the finite element method for the case of a stationary crack. Limited tests indicate that the residual strength or toughness of a DCB specimen is not affected much by temperature over a short time period. Exposure of graphite/epoxy composite to a temperature close to the glass transition temperature of matrix material can cause a drastic reduction in residual strength and time to failure.

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Figure 1. The experimental setup for creep tests

Figure 2. Static load vs. COD curves for (0) specimens

Figure 3. Load vs. COD for (0) specimens prior to creep test

Figure 4. COD as a function of time for (0) specimens

Figure 5. Comparison of test data with finite element results

(a). After 60 hours

(b). After 170 hours

Figure 6. Typical V (opening) displacement fringes from CP-2 specimen

Figure 7. Static load vs. COD curves for (90) specimens

Figure 8. Load vs. COD for (90) specimens prior to creep test

Figure 9. COD as a function of time for (90) specimens

